

MEDICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVEMENT OF FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES OF PARTIALLY REMOVABLE PROSTHESES

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Abstract

The different physicochemical properties of materials and different technologies for their manufacture lead to certain complications in the finished orthopedic appliance, primarily manifested as damage to the prosthetic bed, which in turn results in a decrease in the patient's quality of life.

Keywords; Partially removable denture, mucosal trauma, Gingival margin isolation.

In the case of partial tooth loss, both temporary and permanent removable prostheses are used. Plate dentures are the undisputed leaders in terms of frequency of use for partial and complete tooth replacement in certain categories of patients [3,5]. Modern orthopedic dentistry has a wide range of base materials of various chemical natures for plate dental prostheses. However, scientifically justified approaches to selecting a specific base material for a specific clinical case are lacking [7]. Oral mucosal injuries are one of the main reasons why patients reject removable prostheses [2,4,8]. Imperfections in the clasp fixation, as well as improper edge fitting of the removable prosthesis to natural teeth, lead to the settling of the prosthesis under the influence of vertical chewing forces, which causes trauma or detachment of the gum edge, forming a pathological pocket [1]. Preventing damage to the gingival papilla when making removable plate prostheses for partial tooth loss is an urgent task for dentists. Existing methods in clinical practice are acceptable but insufficiently effective.

Objective of the Study:

The development and implementation of a simple and accessible method in clinical dentistry to effectively isolate the gingival edge of the oral mucosa from trauma caused by removable plate prostheses, and in the dental laboratory, the technology for isolating the base of the removable prosthesis from the prosthetic bed of the oral mucosa.

Materials and Methods:

Fifteen patients with partial removable plate dentures due to partial tooth loss were observed. In the orthopedic dentistry clinic, dynamic monitoring was carried out for 1-2 years. In the dental laboratory, silicone material was used to develop the technology for isolating the base of the removable prosthesis from the prosthetic bed.

Critique of the Existing Method for Isolating the Gingival Edge on Removable Plate Prostheses for Partial Tooth Loss: It is known that the technology for making removable plate prostheses involves complete contact of the base of the prosthesis with the gingival edge of natural teeth. Typically, the finished removable prosthesis clearly outlines the anatomical shape of the

gingival edge of the oral mucosa. The dentist, for fitting such a prosthesis, arbitrarily removes the plastic base layer by layer in the area of contact with the gums until the removable prosthesis fits tightly on the prosthetic bed. At the same time, dentists lack an objective criterion for the contact or lack of contact of the prosthesis base with the oral mucosa. Often, the dentist is guided by the patient's complaints. If the patient experiences pain, the dentist adjusts the base until the patient feels better. Such adjustments to the base and gingival edge result in imperfections, one of which is the uneven contact and the formation of gaps of varying sizes between the base and the gingival edge. Another drawback is the improper tight fitting of the base edges to the natural teeth. The main problem is the misalignment of the prosthetic field with the prosthetic bed. These negative aspects were proven by the method of applying silicone to the surface of the prosthetic bed base and inserting the prosthesis into the mouth. The patient pronounces several words and performs chewing movements during the hardening of the silicone material. Then, the removable prosthesis is removed from the mouth, and we see the uneven filling of silicone between the prosthesis and the gingival edge, with the material leaking into the gaps between the tooth and the prosthesis edge. This situation indicated a complete mismatch of the base to the prosthetic bed.

Proposed Method for Adjusting Removable Prostheses to the Gingival Papilla in Cases of Partial Tooth Loss: In line with the objective of the study, the aim was to optimize the technology for making removable prostheses to ensure their rational fitting in the oral cavity without the need for the dentist's intervention on the finished prosthesis. Several clinical tasks were set to achieve successful orthopedic treatment:

1. The gingival edge of the oral mucosa should not come into contact with the base of the prosthesis, as this leads to trauma to the mucosa.

2. The flexibility of the entire prosthetic bed mucosa during chewing movements must be considered to determine how the prosthesis base moves over the gingival edge. Failing to account for this leads to mucosal injury during chewing movements.

3. The base edge should be positioned above the tooth equator to cushion the chewing load on the prosthesis base.

These tasks are implemented by adjusting the gingival edge on the base of the removable prosthesis during the technological stage of replacing wax with plastic. On the model, where wax is replaced with plastic, after checking the wax construction, a silicone strip of a certain thickness is applied, and then plastic in a paste-like state is applied, followed by polymerization in the traditional manner at the gingival edge of the finished prosthesis. In this case, we will have a space of a specific thickness corresponding to the flexibility of the oral mucosa. Only then can we be sure that during the fitting of the removable prosthesis in the oral cavity, no additional dental interventions are required.

The required thickness for isolating the gingival edge was found in the work of S.A. Naumovich [6], who determined that the amplitude of the oral mucosa's flexibility on the lower jaw ranges from 0.2-0.6 mm. We chose the average flexibility level, which is 0.4 mm, and the isolation is performed to this thickness. Preliminarily, using a parallelometer, we draw a line on the model located above the equator of the natural teeth. Accordingly, on the finished prosthesis, the edge of the removable prosthesis base will be positioned above the tooth equator.

Technological Cycle or Steps for Adjusting Removable Prostheses to the Gingival Edge in Cases of Partial Tooth Loss: All stages of making removable plate prostheses are performed using the classical method. Only during the stage of replacing wax with plastic must the following additional steps be taken:

1. After checking the wax on the model cast in a mold, a pencil is used to mark the boundaries of the base isolation for the future prosthesis. The correction boundary is a line on the model 2.0 mm below the tooth-gum line, including all natural teeth. On the other side, the correction boundary line is drawn above the tooth equator and closed on the supporting teeth on both sides, resulting in a figure of an uncertain shape.

2. The silicone is prepared in a special press mold (Esthetic Mask), designed so that one end has a depth of 0.4 mm, and then the depth decreases and converges to zero after 5.0 mm. Thus, where the prosthesis will come into contact with the gingival edge of the mucosa, the isolation will be 0.4 mm. Closer to the tooth equator, the base will fit tightly to the tooth.

3. Once the silicone takes its final form, it is transferred to the model and placed along the marked boundary. The silicone precisely replicates the drawn shape.

4. Acrylic plastic is mixed, and in a paste-like state, it is packed with subsequent polymerization. It is essential that the gingival edge area of the prosthesis base on the model contacts the silicone surface with a thickness of 0.4 mm, while the part with reduced thickness should be in contact with the natural teeth. After processing, the finished prosthesis is sent to the clinic.

Clinical Application Results: A total of 25 patients aged 50-75 years participated in the study. Ten men and 15 women sought help for poor fixation and function-

ality of their prostheses. Twenty-five percent of patients wished to replace their old prostheses with new ones. Eighty percent of patients required treatment for supporting teeth during prosthesis wear, and some teeth were extracted. The prostheses were used for periods ranging from 3 to 7 years. Patients visited the dentist 3 to 10 times for corrections during prosthesis wear. All patients agreed to have partial removable prostheses made with the gingival edge correction method. Clinical examination and prosthesis manufacturing took place at City Dent Clinic, while dental technical work was performed at the Higher Medical and Dental College laboratory, Prof. Ruzuddinov. All 25 patients received prostheses made from "BMS Dental" acrylic plastic (Italy) and IviclarVivadent (Germany) artificial teeth. Thermally resistant silicone material "Esthetic Mask" (Germany) was used for gingival edge isolation.

Patients who received partial removable prostheses made according to our method noted quick adaptation, improvement in chewing, speech, and the absence of frequent corrections. All had one follow-up visit, where they were instructed on the care and use of the prostheses. No further visits were needed. The follow-up lasted for 1-2 years, with no complaints from patients. All patients remain in contact with the clinic and express satisfaction with the removable prostheses made for them.

Conclusion: We propose that clinicians who provide treatment with partial removable prostheses use our method for "Correction of the Gingival Edge on Removable Prostheses for Partial Tooth Loss." This method is not labor-intensive, and its clinical effect is quite successful.

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